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The Tradition of Nyaya in Kerala

Niveditha Sathyan¹

Kerala's contribution in Sanskrit literature is very rich and diverse. Studies are available in all branches such as Kavya, Nataka, Campu and the technical literature such as Vyakarana, Tantra, Mantra, Silpa, Ganita and Vaidya. Sanskrit, as a language flourished in Kerala with the Brahmins and their Vedic culture. They came from outside in an early period and Sanskrit existed as the basic language for many years for the spiritual, social as well as cultural learning in Kerala (Ullur 4).

The Namboothiri Brahmins of Kerala enjoyed supremacy in the spiritual and social hierarchy and were well versed in the arts of war and peace. Due to their special kind of family setup they were free from the problems of everyday life, so they could spend their entire time on the creation of Literature and Arts. Royal families in Kerala were also responsible for the rich contribution to Sanskrit Literature.

Many of the temples under Namboothiri management provided facilities for teaching of Vedas and Sastras. The Brahmaswam Mathom situated in Thrissur was a center for Vedic study. The Kolathiris in the north, the Zamorins of Calicut, the members of Cochin Royal Family in the central part and Thiruvithamkoor rulers in the south were some of the rulers who promoted and supported the study of Sanskrit in Kerala.

Ancient Centers in Traditional Learning

The learning of Sanskrit was undertaken in the traditional way and for every Sastras there existed many traditional centers. They are-

Payyur

In the history of Sanskrit literature, the payyur Bhatta's family

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had played a significant role most importantly in the study of *Purva Mimamsa*. There were a lot of great poets as well as scholars in that family and their contribution to *Mimamsa* literature and Sanskrit poetry is immense both in volume and in depth.

The family of the Payyur Bhattas is located near to Porkalam around sixteen miles away from the north-western part of Thrissur. Their village is called as Valangad and there exist a temple for the Goddess *Gopalika* (Kunjunni Raja 91). Dr Kunjunni Raja remarks that the earliest member of the Payyur Bhattas family about whom we have some literary reference is Risi I. He had a brother who was a great scholar in *Vedanta* named Bhavadasa. Risi I married Gauri and they had a son named Parameswara-I.

Kutallur

Kutallur is another famous traditional learning Centre which is to be mentioned here. Kutallur Mana, the family of Nampootiri Brahmins is known for the study of *Vyakarana*. This family is known as *Sangamalaya* in Sanskrit and is located at Nagasreni which is generally known as Nareni near Pattambi. The Kutallur Nambootiris were known and noted to be the descendants of Mezhatol Agnihotri. They, with their proficiency and scholarship in Sanskrit and Sastras and with their efficient teaching methodology, contributed much to Sanskrit literature mostly in *Vyakarana*.

The study of *Vyakarana* under the Gurukula system was highly efficient and was praised by the scholars. There is a verse in praise of the Gurukula system.

“*Kaumudi pipatisa yadi te syadabdapanchakamananyavicara
Sangamalayamahisurageham gacca vatsamuciram subhamastu*”
(Vdakkumkooor vol.V, .556).

This Gurukula was famous not only for the study of *Kaumudi*, but also for the higher studies in *Vyakarana*. It was the only abode in Kerala.

Tradition of Nyaya Sastra in Kerala

The study of *Vyakarana*, *mimamsa* etc. were prevalent in Kerala, but study of *Nyaya* was not much popular. The *sabhamathoms* did

not include *Nyaya* as a subject for study in their curriculum. Yet there are some references about the scholars of *Nyaya*. *Vadakkumkur Rajavarma* states that the books written on *Nyaya* were not written by Keralites and the study of *Nyaya* was not that much popular (Vdakkumkoor Vol.VI, 502). But we can see in many places *Vadakkumkur* mentions many authors who have studied *Tarka* from somebody. So *Tarka* was studied and many had basic knowledge of *Tarka Sastra*. Kumbhakonam Krisnasastry is described as the student of Vidvan Elaya Tamapuran by Vadakkamkur (Vdakkumkoor vol.IV, 317). It is also stated by *Vadakkumkur* that Mutukurussi Bhaskaran Nampootiri was a student of a 'Mani Tampuran' of Kozhikode. He was called Mani Tampuran because he was well versed in "*Cintamani*" a *Nyaya grantha* (Vdakkumkoor 306).

Moreover, the style and methodology of *Navya Nyaya* can be seen in the works of other Sastras. As the study of Sanskrit language and Sastras flourished under royal patronage, the study of *Nyaya* also got entrance to the royal courts at a later period. The study of *Nyaya* in Kerala was popularized with these scholars of Kumbhakonam. Kumbhakonam KrisnaSastry and Satakopacarya were appointed as *Nyaya* teachers in the Kotungallur Kovilakam. Trippunithura acquired eminence in the study of *Nyaya* from three routed scholars from Tamil Nadu viz. Sesacarya, Sataakopacarya and Rangappacarya (Ullur Vol.V, 221). Sesacarya's grandson Setumadhavadiksitar, famous *Nyaya* scholar was the friend of Pariksit Rama Varman and Sastr Sarman.

The famous *Nyaya* scholars of Kerala viz. Bhattan Tampuran of Kotungallur, Rajarsi Ramavarma and Pariksit Ramavarma from Trippunithura are the disciples of these scholars who came to Kerala seeking patronage.

Kotungallur Gurukulam

The *Kotungallur Kovilkam* was known as the Taksasila of South India in the eighteenth century A.D for being a centre for the distribution of all kinds of traditional knowledge. The rulers of that family were great scholars and patrons. A number of scholars depending on them served a lot for the propagation of the study

of *Sastra, Kavya* and *Sangita*. Later it came to be known as the *Kotungallur Gurukulam* (Vadakkumkooor Vol.IV, 312). The great scholars like Kavisarvabhauma Kochunni Raja, Kunjikuttan Thampuran famous as Kerala Vyasa, Valiyakocunni Raja, great scholar in Astronomy were some of the teachers that adorned this Gurukulam. Godavarma Elaya Tampuran, Godavarma Bhattan Tampuran were the great scholars in Nyaya.

Panditarajan Mantitta Kunju Nampootiri- the famous *Naiyayika*, Attur Krisna Pisharody- famous as Ubhayakaviswara were the disciples of the above said scholars who later became more famous than their teachers.

Godavarma Vidvan Yuvraja and Godavarma Bhattan Tampuran were the important Nyaya scholars from *Kotungallur Gurukulam*.

Godavarma Vidvan Yuvraja (1800 A.D)

Godavarma Vidvan Yuvaraja was a successful scholar in various areas of learning like *Jyotisa, Kavya, Silpa, Vaidya* and was famous as a *Naiyayika* by his work '*Hetvabhasasodaharana*'. He was born in 1800 A.D. and his parents were Elankurussi Matrdatta Nampootiri and Vidusi Kunjikkutty Tampuratty. His famous disciples were Kumbhakonam Krishna Sastry, a famous teacher, and *Paccumusat* another scholar and composer of many books (Vadakkumkooor Vol.V, 317).

Vadakkumkur mentions about fifteen works of this great scholar viz. *Ramacarita, Hetvabhasa, Sri Padasaptakam, Sudhanandalahari, Rasasadnam, Goladhyaya* etc (Vdakkumkooor 318). Among these *hetvabhasasodaharana* is a work which deals with the fallacies of *hetu*. It gives the slokas as examples for *Hetvabhasas*. *Hetvabhasa* is an important topic in the Nyaya system which is included in the *Anumana Pramana*. There are five kinds of *hetvabhasas* viz. *savyabhicara, viruddha, satpratipaksa, asiddha* and *badhita*. Vadakkumkur qouts three *karikas* from that book. Among them the first one is-

“Tvam rustva mayi cennamami dayite neyam tvaya namyatam
Namyatvam tvayi bhathi parthivataya manye maharajavat.
Kumbhadistativartanat tvaduditam sadharanam sadhanam

Vagevadesviti nirjito dayitaya ramasukham ratu vah”

(Vdakkumkooor 317).

Godavarma Bhattan Tampuran(1858 A.D)

Godavarma Bhattan Tampuran of Kotungallur Kovilakam was a famous scholar in many sastras especially in Nyaya Sastra. He was born in 1858 A.D. and his parents were Akkarakkurissi Raman Nampootiri and Smt. Kunjikkutti Rajni. His first guru was his own father. *Rajarsi Ramavarma* of Cochin Palace taught *Vyakarana* and Nyaya. Godavarma Bhattan Tampuran gained deep knowledge in Nyaya from Kumbhakonam Sadakopacarya. A *karika* in *Siddhantamala* shows his devotion to that teacher (Raja, Karika 3).² Ullur remarks that even Rajarsi Ramavarma, a famous scholar in Nyaya approached Bhattan Tampuran to clear his doubts in Nyaya (Ullur Vol.V, .224).

Godavarma Bhattan Tampuran composed about 12 books viz. *Upaharaprakasikavyakhya*, *Saktiprakasika*, *Bhagavata pradhamasloka vyakhya*, *Nyayaratnavali vyakhya*, *Pramanavada vyakhya* and *Siddhantamala*. The *Pramanyavada vyakhya* is a Nyaya work, but that was not published.

Godavarma Bhattan Tampuran composed the commentary in the Karika form with all the theories proposed by Gadhadharabhata. It contains 7 *prakaranas* and 495 *karikas*. The first *karika* is a *mangalasloka* includes the concept of *sakti* is the power of word (Raja Karika 1).³

Nyaya scholars from Trippunithura

The Nyaya tradition is popularized in Trippunithura by the eminent Nyaya scholar Sesacarya from Kumbhakonam. Sesacarya taught Nyaya to the Maharaja of Cochin, Rajarsi Rama Varman. Among the Sanskrit scholars of Cochin Royal family, two kings should be significantly mentioned for studying and popularizing Sanskrit language and especially Nyaya Sastra. They are Rajarsi Ramavarman and Pariksit Ramavarman.

2. *Aśyava satakopakhyagurukarunyato
Mama samarthamidriśo karmanyatigandamaterahi’*

3. *‘yadicchayaiva sabdanamarthopāśhītitihetuta
Sarvesam sa sivo bhuyadarthopāśhītitaye’*

Rajarsi Ramavarman (1852-1931)

Rajarsi Ramavarman was born in 1852 to Kotalathpurath Bhaskaran Nampootiripad and Ambalika Tampuratty. He was a great scholar, a patron of learning and an efficient ruler, who adorned the royal palace of Cochin. His reign was praised as the golden age for the study of Sanskrit literature and especially for Nyaya Sastra. He studied Nyaya Sastra from Sesacarya. His significant contribution to the study of Sastra is the establishment of *Samskrta Pathasala*. Rajarsi Ramavarman established the *sastra Mahapathasala* which offered advanced instruction in three Sastras viz. *Nyaya, Vyakarana and Vedanta*. Sankara Narayana Sastry as lecture in Nyaya and Vyakarana. Only two books of Rajarsi Ramavarman are available. They are, 1. *Vedanta Paribhasa Sangraha*, 2. *Balabodhana*.

Pariksit Ramavarman (1876)

Pariksit Ramavarman also known as Ramavarma Kunjunni Thampuran was born in 1876 A.D. as the son of Ottur Raman Nampootiripad. He was a great scholar and the last Maharaja of Cochin and is accepted as the author of many works in Nyaya Sastra. His Nyaya works are- *Subodhini, Jalavathrdaniscayatva vicara, and Bhumika* to the work of Sastr Sarman.

Subodhini is a commentary on *Muktavali*. Later the *Subodhini* can be considered as a *Guru Saparya* which means offering to the Guru (Pariksit 1). *Jalavathrdaniscayatva vicara* is a small work dealing with a special topic in the *hetvabhasa prakarana*. The next contribution of Pariksit Ramavarman is *Bhumika*, written for the *Nacaratnamalika* of Sastr sarman. It is a small essay regarding many contemporary problems the traditional Sastric study has to face.

Mantitta Kunju Nampootiri (1876-1959)

Sastr sarman or Panditarajan Mantitta Kunju Nampootiri is a famous *Naiyayika* from Kerala in the nineteenth century A.D. The family name is Mantitta. Sastr sarman was known by the pet-name *Kunju* in his childhood and sarman is the term added to denote brahmins (Kuñcunampūtiri *Alokaprakasa*, .24).⁴ His *Nacaratnamalika* is really a valuable contribution to the wealth of

4 *sarmantam brahmananam iti smritimanusrutya sastrusarmetyuktam*

‘*Vada prastana*’. Sarma studied Nyaya under GBT. Sarma was a regular participant in the *Sastra Sadas* at Trippunithura. Sarma was appointed as the professor of Nyaya in *Sree Sesacarya Samskrta Pathasala* by Rjarsi Tampuran. His disciples were T.Rama Warriar, C.K Raman Nambiar, K. Acyuta Potuval and P.C. Vasudevan Elayth.

K Ramapisaroty (1876-1947) and Cennamangalam Ayya Sastrikal (1864-1945) were other Nyaya scholars entitled by Rajarsi Ramavarman and Sastrsarman as *Sahridayatilaka and Sabdikatilaka*.

Works of K.Ramapisaroty-Ramavarma *dasaka khanda kavya, Tippani* for *Citramimamsa, Dinakariya* and *Vyutpattivada*.

P S Ananda Narayana Sastry (1885-1957)

P.S.Ananda Narayana Sastry is another Nyaya scholar. He is a contemporary of Sastr sarman. *Tarkasara* is a work in Nyaya written by him. In the beginning of *Tarkasara* he says that ‘it is written for the use of beginners who wish to study Nyaya’.

C K Raman Nambiar (1900)

CK Raman Nambiar was a reputed Nyaya scholar who contributed to the *Nacaratnamalika* in the form of the sub-commentary *Alokaprakasa*. He was a professor of Nyaya in the Sanskrit College, Trippunithura. He was the chief editor of the journal, *Ravivarma Samskrta Grandavali*, and contributed many short essays and slokas to it. Raman Nambiar further holds that *Paniniyam* is used to know the proper words to denote the objects and *Kanada* is conducive to know the object and thereby the right knowledge can be attained by these sastras (Pariksit 4).⁵

K Acyuta Potuval (1898-1972)

K Acyuta Potuval is a disciple of Sastr sarman, and Meledath Govindan Nambiar. He was appointed as the professor of Nyaya in the *Sesacarya Mahapathasala*.

T Rama Warriar (1897-1978)

Trikovil Rama Warriar was a respected Ayurvedic physician in Trippunithura. He was also a Nyaya scholar who joined with C K Raman Nambiar and K Acyuta Potuval to compose the commentary

⁵ *kanadam paniniyam ca sarvasatropakarakam,*

for *Ncaratnamalika*. He studied Nyaya and qualified *Nyayabhusana* from *Samskrta Pathasala*.

Conclusion

Kerala has a varied contribution to Sanskrit literature, especially in Nyaya Sastra. Nyaya study was not very popular in the beginning. But later Nyaya was appreciated much in Kerala by many Nyaya scholars viz. Bhattan Tampuran of Kotungallur, Rjarsi Ramavarma and Pariksit Ramavarma from Trippunithura. Thus the scholars of Nyaya contributed a lot for the propagation and development of the Nyaya Sastra. Their contributions are from the existing Sastra works. The Legacy continues in Kerala through the contemporary Naiyayikas who are inspired by the great predecessors from whom they received the torch flame of the tradition.

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